

AN INVESTIGATION FOR UNIVERSITY STUDENTS' SELF PERCEPTIONS OF SOCIAL MEDIA ADDICTION

Necmi Esgi

College of Education, Computer and Instructional Technologies Department,
Gazi Osman Paşa University, Turkey

Abstract:

The aim of the study is to examine the self-perceptions of university students about social media addiction who are aged between 18 and 21 and up. In the research, the social media addiction scale was employed in order to determine students' self-perceptions. The scale was administered to 180 students. Of the participant students in the research, 25% described themselves as individuals experiencing problems in Social media addiction. On the other hand, it was determined that the factors of age, gender and socioeconomic level create no significant differences in students' self-perceptions, I indicate the predicting leadership style with organizational health.

Keywords: social media addiction, university students, self-perceptions

1. Introduction

In the most general definition, social media is the platform that was used to share data synchronously or asynchronously. Also, social media can be defined as a medium that a content created by one user can be modified and redistributed by other users. In this environments, users share according to their preferences and choices. Most common of these platforms are Facebook and Twitter.

Internet addiction is composed of different addiction types such as game addiction, and social media addiction. Social media addiction is considered to be a sub part of internet addiction or a specific case of internet addiction (Wilson, 2015).

Seferoglu and Yildiz (2013) found that there was a linear relationship between primary school students' internet use and social media use, in a social media addiction study. Rouis et al (2011) suggested that Facebook use effect the academic success negatively; but effects the life satisfaction positively. Akdemir (2013) found that

Facebook use affects the academic success negatively on primary school students. Literature review conducted about the social media addiction of college students showed that very few studies were conducted about the topic. For this reason the study goal, was applying social media addiction scale to college students and discussing the result.

2. Method and instruments

The "Social Media Usage Scale" developed by Esgi (2016) and consisting of 17 items was employed in this research. It is composed of four sub-factors (Time, Social sharing, Job, Health) It is a 4-point Likert-type scale: 1 (never), 2 (rarely), 3 (sometimes), 4 (often). Social media addiction scale was administered in a pre-trial group that consisted of 285 participants, and its internal reliability coefficient was found to be (a) .94. The scores that can be obtained from the scale ranged from 17 to 68. The base-line score in evaluation of scores was determined as 18 and above, in other words, an individual with a score of 18 or above was considered to be someone who perceived themselves as experiencing social media addiction problems. Students' self- perceptions were examined on the basis of gender, socioeconomic level, age, and grade level. The impacts of the factors on the group scores were analyzed using t-test, variance analysis and mean distribution.

3. Findings and interpretation

3.1. Findings related to demographic information about students

Demographic Information about students is given in Table 1.

Table 1: Demographic Information about Students

Gender		Grade Level				Socioeconomic Level			Age			
Male	Female	Freshmen	Sophomore	Junior	Senior	Low	Middle	Upper	18	19	20	21 and up
88	92	48	49	47	36	50	95	35	45	48	49	38

The participants of the research were 180 students attending four different grade level from Gazi Osman Pasa University (95 female and 85 male). Of these students, 48 attended freshmen, 49 sophomore and 47 junior, 36 senior. 50 of the participant students came from lower, 95 middle and 35 upper socio-economic backgrounds. In addition, 45 participants were 18 years old, whereas 48 were 19, 49 were 20, and 38 were 21 and up.

3.2. Findings related to students' self-perceptions

3.2.1 Distribution

Distribution and percentages of the students' scores are presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Distribution of students' scores

17 points		18-68 points	
%	f	%	f
75	145	25	45

As indicated in Table 2, 75% of the students (145 people) perceived themselves as average social media user (17 points and down). In addition, 25% (45) perceived themselves as users who experience serious problems in social media-use (18-68 points).

3.2.2 Age

The comparison of students' scores with respect to their age levels is given in Table 3.

Table 3: Comparison of students' scores with respect to age

Source of the variance	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	P
Between Groups	686.374	3	228.7	2.07	.10
Within Groups	19430.620	176	110.4		
Total	20116.994	179			

As it is seen in Table 3, the results of analysis indicate that there is no statistically significant difference between the mean scores received by 18-year-olds ($\bar{x}=35.30$), 19-year-olds ($\bar{x}=35.76$), and 20-year-olds ($\bar{x}=32.75$), 21 and upper -year-olds ($\bar{x}=30.75$) [$F_{3-179}=2.07$, $p>.05$].

3.2.3 Gender

Table 4: Comparison of students' scores with respect to gender

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Sd	t	P
Male	88	34.82	10.91	178	1.4	.27
Female	92	32.56	10.06			

The comparison of students' scores with respect to the gender factor is given in Table 4. Table 4 shows that there is no significant difference between students' scores in terms of gender [$t_{178}=1.4$, $p>.05$] Girls' scores ($=32.56$), and boys' scores ($=34.82$).

3.2.4 Socio-economic level

The comparison of students' scores with respect to their socioeconomic levels is given in Table 5.

Table 5: Impacts of different socioeconomic levels on participants' scores

Source of the variance	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	P
Between Groups	161,25	2	80.62	.71	.49
Within Groups	19955,74	177	112.74		
Total	20116,99	179			

No significant difference was found between the mean scores received by students coming from lower socioeconomic background ($=33.91$), middle socioeconomic background ($=32.92$), and upper socioeconomic background ($=37.08$) [$F_{2-179}=.49$, $p>.05$]. This finding indicates that children's socio-economic levels do not have impact on the intensity of Social media addiction.

4. Conclusion

It was determined, with the general limitations of the research, that 45 of 180 university students aged between 18 and 21 consider themselves as experiencing problems in terms of social media addiction. It means 25 percent of all students have social media addiction. It is indeed a very high number.

Yet another notable point is that differences in socioeconomic level, age and gender do not have impact on social media addiction. This finding can be explained by the fact that people from lower socioeconomic background now have equal access to social media technologies. Also same explanation is valid for the factors of gender and age.

In conclusion, when all the findings are here considered together, it is believed that social media addiction is growing. People should be informed and educated about social media addiction issues.

About the Author

Assoc. Prof. Dr. Necmi Eşgi, working at Gazi Osman Paşa University, College of Education, Computer and Instructional Technologies Department, Turkey, email address necmiesgi@gmail.com, Interested in Social, media, Internet, Addiction, Instructional Design, Instructional Material Development.

References

1. Akdemir, N. Tekin (2013). İlköğretim Öğrencilerinin Facebook Tutumları İle Akademik Erteleme Davranışları ve Akademik Başarıları Arasındaki İlişkilerin İncelenmesi. Yayımlanmamış Yüksek Lisans Tezi, Bilgisayar ve Öğretim Teknolojileri Eğitimi Bilim Dalı, Eğitim Bilimleri Enstitüsü. Marmara Üniversitesi, İstanbul.
2. Rouis, S.; Limayem, M. ve Sangari, S. Esmail. (2011). "Impact of Facebook Usage on Students' Academic Achievement: Roles of Self-Regulation And Trust." Education & Psychology I+D+i and Editorial EOS (Spain). 9(3), 961-994.
3. Seferoglu, Süleyman S. ve Yıldız, H. (2013). "Dijital Çağın Çocukları: İlköğretim Öğrencilerinin Facebook Kullanım Durumları ve İnternet Bağımlılıkları Üzerine Bir Araştırma." İletişim ve Diplomasi / Çocuk ve Medya. 31-48.
4. [http://yunus.hun.edu.tr/~sadi/yayin/Seferoglu-Yildiz Dijital-CaginCocuklari_Ilet_ve_Diplomasi-2013](http://yunus.hun.edu.tr/~sadi/yayin/Seferoglu-Yildiz_Dijital-CaginCocuklari_Ilet_ve_Diplomasi-2013)
5. Wilson, L. (2015) Social Media Addiction. <http://drlwilson.com/ARTICLES/ADDITION%20SOCIAL%20M.htm>

Creative Commons licensing terms

Author(s) will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of Education Studies shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflicts of interest, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated into the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).